

S Fig. 1. Forest plot displaying the TSMR analysis results for the effect of antibodies against EBV on ANDs. The analysis was conducted using TSMR, with a Bonferroni-corrected significance threshold set at $P = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$

S Fig. 2 MR estimate results of Anti-EBV IgG seropositivity on MS.

S Fig. 3 MR estimate results of EBV EA-D antibody levels on MS.

S Fig. 4 MR estimate results of EBV EBNA-1 antibody levels on MS.

S Fig. 5 MR estimate results of EBV VCA p18 antibody levels on MS.

S Fig. 6 MR estimate results of EBV ZEBRA antibody levels on MS.

S Fig. 7 MR estimate results of Anti-EBV IgG seropositivity on NMO.

S Fig. 8 MR estimate results of EBV EA-D antibody levels on NMO.

S Fig. 9 MR estimate results of EBV EBNA-1 antibody levels on NMO.

S Fig. 10 MR estimate results of EBV VCA p18 antibody levels on NMO.

S Fig. 11 MR estimate results of EBV ZEBRA antibody levels on NMO.